

STUDENTS' METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE THROUGH GAME-BASED LEARNING IN GRADE 10 SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Game-based learning is an educational approach designed to enhance students' understanding of a subject while engaging them in interactive and guided experiences. This study investigated the effects of game-based learning on students' metacognitive awareness and academic performance in Grade 10 science. Specifically, it aimed to determine the students' level of metacognitive awareness when exposed to game-based and non-game-based learning in terms of declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge; assess academic performance through pretest, posttest, and retention test; and analyze significant differences between the two groups. A quasi-experimental research design was used, involving two groups: one exposed to non-game-based learning and the other to game-based learning. Instruments included both academic and non-academic assessments. Descriptive statistics such as weighted means, percentages, and standard deviation were used, while ANCOVA determined significant differences in metacognitive awareness and academic performance. Results showed that both groups improved in metacognitive awareness after the intervention, with the GBL group showing slightly higher posttest means across all subskills, indicating better organization, strategy monitoring, and study management. In academic performance, GBL students scored higher than non-GBL students, though both groups' mean percentage scores remained below the "meet expectations" level. Retention rates were also higher among GBL students, suggesting that interactive learning strengthens long-term recall in science. Overall, game-based learning can enhance metacognitive awareness and support academic performance but may require further reinforcement to reach proficiency.

Keywords: *Game-Based Learning, Metacognitive Awareness, Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced digital world, capturing students' attention and fostering interest in learning has become essential. Science, a subject that thrives on curiosity and discovery, requires innovative way to enhance engagement and enrich the teaching and learning processes. Game-based learning (GBL) has emerged as a powerful tool in modern education, transforming passive learners into active participants through interactive challenges and problem-solving tasks. To achieve goals pertaining to global competitiveness of learners, the Philippines must give top priority to enhance its science education.

The 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) results from the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) revealed that the Philippines struggles in science, ranking among the lowest-performing countries. Also, Simbajon and Adlaon (2024) analyzed the PISA 2022 results and found that most Filipino students performed at Level 1 and Level 2, which indicate low to basic proficiency in science. Only a few reached Level 3 and Level 4, which show intermediate to advanced skills. This suggests that many students still struggle to understand and apply scientific concepts. Similarly, Casildo (2022) examines national data from the National Achievement Test (NAT), reveals a score of 32.11%, highlighting gaps in knowledge and application and showing low competency in science. At the regional level, the Division of Bukidnon has reported similar concerns, with student performance in science remaining challenging. The study of Añar et al. (2023) stated in general that primary and secondary basic education learners did poorly on the NAT, demonstrating poor critical thinking, problem-solving, and information literacy skills.

Recent studies highlight that students engaged in digital game-based learning (DGBL) exhibit significant improvements in academic outcomes compared to traditional learning methods. In the Philippine context, Vilanueva (2024) reported that Grade 11 students exposed to game-based learning in Earth and Life Science classes demonstrated notable improvements in academic performance compared to those under traditional instruction. These findings underscore the potential of game-based learning (GBL) as an effective pedagogical approach to boost both engagement and achievement in science education.

However, despite these promising developments, challenges in science education remain evident at the local level. The consistent low performance in science calls for innovative and engaging instructional strategies that not only enhance students' comprehension but also strengthen their academic performance and metacognitive skills. Given this context, exploring the effects of game-based learning could provide valuable insights into improving science education outcomes. By integrating games into the learning process, students ask questions, make observations, explore data, and

manipulate information, which fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Makalintal et al. 2019). One major advantage of GBL is its potential to provide students with real-world applications of their acquired knowledge, thereby reinforcing higher-order thinking skills (Cruz, 2023). However, further studies are needed to assess the most effective ways to implement GBL across various learning environments and measure its long-term impact (Al-Khayat et al. 2023).

Despite the potential of GBL to foster metacognitive development, several studies have reported that many students, particularly in science, struggle with low levels of metacognitive awareness, which contributes to poor academic performance (Zepeda et al. 2015). Saaidin (2020) emphasized that students with low metacognitive control often fail to monitor their comprehension and regulate their learning effectively, resulting in lower academic outcomes. In the Philippine context, science education continues to face similar challenges, as students often demonstrate difficulty in applying learning strategies that support understanding and retention. Furthermore, a study by Taran and Nalla (2019) found that while senior high school students exhibited high levels of metacognitive awareness, their attitudes toward problem-solving in science were only moderate, suggesting a gap between awareness and the effective application of learning strategies.

These findings highlight the ongoing need to enhance instructional methods that foster both metacognitive skills and academic performance. However, limited research has been conducted in local public-school settings, particularly in rural areas creating a gap in the literature regarding the effectiveness of GBL in improving both metacognitive awareness and academic performance in this context. Adopting innovative and engaging instructional strategies such as GBL becomes crucial in addressing students' metacognitive gaps and supporting better learning outcomes.

This study examines the effectiveness of Game-Based Learning (GBL) as an intervention to enhance Grade 10 students' metacognitive awareness focusing on declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge and to improve their academic performance in science. By investigating the impact of GBL on both cognitive and academic outcomes, the study contributes valuable insights to the field of science education.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of students' metacognitive awareness between those engaged in game-based learning and those in non-game-based learning in terms of declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge and conditional knowledge?
2. What is the level of students' academic performance as exposed to game-based learning and those exposed to non-game-based learning in terms of pretest, posttest and retention test?
3. Is there a significant difference in students' metacognitive awareness when exposed to game-based learning and non-game-based learning, with pretest as covariates?

4. Is there a significant difference in students' academic performance when exposed to game-based learning and non-game-based learning, with pretest as covariate?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at the rural area of Don Carlos, Bukidnon in the southern part of the Philippines. approximately 460 meters west of Sayre Highway. As a public institution, it serves the educational needs of nearby communities by offering both Junior High School and Senior High School programs. The Senior High School department provides academic strands in Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) and Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL). The school has seven buildings, including around 21 classrooms and basic laboratory facilities.

The study employed a quasi-experimental research design that included a pre-test, post-test, and test to assess the effects of game-based learning on students' metacognitive awareness. Two heterogeneous sections of Grade 10 participated in the study, with one section involved in game-based learning (GBL) and the other in non-game-based learning (non-GBL). Two instruments were employed, namely, the academic and non-academic assessments.

In measuring students' academic performance, a 100-item multiple-choice test was constructed based on the eight (8) competencies outlined in the second quarter of the Grade 10 Science Curriculum. The topics included the Electromagnetic Spectrum, Light, Electricity, and Magnetism. A Table of Specifications (TOS) was created based on the cognitive domain level of the relevant learning competencies. To assess students' academic performance, the researcher-made exam underwent item analysis, resulting in a final set of 50 test items. The test questionnaire's content was verified by three local experts. It was pilot tested to Grade 10 students at ONNHS to verify its reliability. The test questionnaire's reliability is demonstrated by its Reliability coefficient of 0.72. These items were then administered as pretests and posttests to the two participant groups. Two (2) weeks after the posttest, the researcher administered the retention test to measure how well students remembered and retained information over time after learning it. The study follows the standards established in DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015, when interpreting the data obtained.

In measuring non-academic assessment, A 30-item metacognitive awareness assessment adapted from Maniego (2021) was used to evaluate students' levels of metacognitive awareness. It included three indicators, each comprising ten statements: declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge areas. The assessment employed a 4-point Likert scale, with options ranging from "at all times" to "never".

The study employed descriptive statistics, including frequency values, percentages, means, and standard deviations, to collect information on students' metacognitive awareness. It used Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to assess whether significant differences existed between students' metacognitive awareness when

exposed to Game-Based Learning and Non-game-based Learning. The pre-test results were covariates in determining students' metacognitive awareness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Students' Metacognitive Awareness Towards Science

Declarative Knowledge

Table 1 presents students' metacognitive awareness in science regarding declarative knowledge, comparing the effects of game-based learning (GBL) and non-game-based learning (non-GBL). The pretest mean score for declarative knowledge in the GBL group was 2.57, indicating *High Cognitive Awareness*, while the posttest mean score increased to 3.03, maintaining the *High Cognitive Awareness* rating. Similarly, the non-GBL group had a pretest mean score of 2.51 (*Low Cognitive Awareness*), which improved to 2.92 (*High Cognitive Awareness*) in the posttest. These results indicate that both instructional strategies contributed to enhancing students' declarative knowledge.

Table 1. Students' metacognitive awareness level under declarative

Indicators	Pretest		Posttest					
	GBL	Non-GBL	GBL	Non-GBL	GBL	Non-GBL	GBL	Non-GBL
	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI
I learn more when I am interested in the topic.	3.18	H	2.89	H	3.62	VH	3.21	H
I organize my time to accomplish my goals.	2.91	H	2.78	H	3.29	VH	3.03	H
I understand my intellectual strengths and weaknesses.	2.65	H	2.61	H	3.06	H	2.85	H
I know what kind of information is most important to learn.	2.62	H	2.57	H	3.35	VH	3.09	H
I consider several alternatives to a problem before I answer.	2.56	L	2.30	L	3.06	H	2.88	H
I have control over how I will learn.	2.50	L	2.47	L	3.03	H	2.91	H
I know what the teacher expects me to learn.	2.47	L	2.44	L	2.71	H	3.18	H
I am good at remembering information.	2.41	L	2.44	L	2.76	H	2.71	H
I am good judge of how well I understand something.	2.38	L	2.35	L	2.91	H	2.62	H

I am good at organizing information.	2.00	L	2.29	L	2.53	H	2.74	H
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.57	H	2.51	H	3.03	H	2.92	H

<u>Legend:</u>	<u>Descriptive Rating</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
<u>Range</u>	All the time	Very High (VH)
3.26 - 4.00	Most of the time	High (H)
2.51 - 3.25	Sometime	Low (L)
1.76 - 2.50	Never	Very Low (VL)
1.00 - 1.75		

In the GBL group, the highest posttest scores were observed in *I learn more when I am interested in the topic* (3.62), *I know what kind of information is most important to learn* (3.35), and *I organize my time to accomplish my goals* (3.29). This suggests that game-based learning effectively fostered student engagement, improved their ability to identify key information, and encouraged better time management.

Game-based learning, as a form of interactive and meaningful activity, creates a context where students internalize declarative knowledge more effectively. Additionally, indicators that initially had lower mean scores in the pretest but showed significant improvement in the posttest include *I consider several alternatives to a problem before I answer* (from 2.56 to 3.06), *I have control over how I will learn* (from 2.50 to 3.03), *I am a good judge of how well I understand something* (from 2.38 to 2.91), and *I know what the teacher expects me to learn* (from 2.47 to 2.71). This pattern suggests that as students engaged in game-based learning, they became more reflective about their understanding and developed stronger self-regulation skills.

For the non-GBL group, the posttest scores also demonstrated a positive trend across all indicators. The highest-scoring items were *I learn more when I am interested in the topic* (3.21), *I know what the teacher expects me to learn* (3.18), and *I organize my time to accomplish my goals* (3.03). This indicates that even without game-based interventions, students still developed metacognitive awareness through structured instruction. This finding is supported by Abdelshiheed et al. (2023), who emphasized that explicit instruction and structured strategies can lead to increased metacognitive awareness even without gamified elements. However, despite overall improvements, some indicators remained relatively lower for both groups, particularly *I am good at organizing information* (GBL: 2.53, non-GBL: 2.74) and *I am a good judge of how well I understand something* (GBL: 2.91, non-GBL: 2.62). This suggests that while students improved in their declarative knowledge, challenges in organizing and assessing their own learning persisted.

The findings highlight that both game-based and non-game-based learning approaches effectively enhance students' metacognitive awareness. However, GBL appears to provide additional benefits in promoting interest, time management, and self-directed learning. Meanwhile, the results for the non-GBL group suggest that traditional teaching methods can also support metacognitive growth, although some areas may require further reinforcement. These findings support Abdelshiheed et al.'s (2023) study, which suggests that explicit instruction and structured strategies can enhance students'

metacognitive awareness. The implication for classroom practice is that educators may consider integrating game-based activities to supplement traditional instruction, especially when aiming to cultivate student engagement and self-directed learning habits. Hence, future research may explore additional scaffolding techniques to help students further develop their ability to organize and evaluate their learning progress, particularly in non-GBL settings where some metacognitive domains showed less pronounced improvement.

Procedural Knowledge

Table 2 displays the mean scores of students' metacognitive awareness in procedural knowledge, comparing game-based learning (GBL) with non-game-based learning (non-GBL). The pretest mean score for the non-GBL group was 2.43, indicating *Low Cognitive Awareness*, while the posttest mean score rose to 2.87, reflecting *High Cognitive Awareness*. Similarly, the GBL group recorded a pretest mean score of 2.53, categorized as *High Cognitive Awareness*, which improved to 2.99 in the posttest. These results show that both groups enhanced their procedural knowledge, indicating increased metacognitive awareness following the intervention. This supports the assertion by Stiller and Schworm (2019) that active engagement through structured tasks, such as games or traditional lessons, fosters metacognitive gains.

Table 2. Students' metacognitive awareness level under procedural knowledge

Indicators	Pretest				Posttest			
	GBL		Non-GBL		GBL		Non-GBL	
	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI
I read instructions carefully before I begin a task.	3.06	H	2.50	L	3.41	VH	2.97	H
I periodically review to help me understand important relationship.	2.71	H	2.50	L	3.00	H	2.88	H
I think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one.	2.68	H	2.53	H	3.03	H	2.91	H
I think about what I need to learn before I begin a task.	2.56	H	2.62	H	3.09	H	2.97	H
I am aware of what strategies I use when I study.	2.56	H	2.32	L	3.09	H	2.88	H
I ask myself questions about the material before I begin.	2.44	L	2.44	L	2.79	H	2.65	H
I find myself using helpful learning strategies automatically.	2.44	L	2.47	L	3.06	H	2.76	H
I have a specific purpose for each strategy I use.	2.41	L	2.29	L	2.76	H	2.65	H
I try to use strategies that have worked in the past.	2.35	L	2.38	L	2.85	H	2.97	H

I pace myself while learning to have enough time.	2.06	L	2.23	L	2.82	H	3.09	H
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.53	H	2.43	L	2.99	H	2.87	H

Legend:

<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Rating</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
3.26 - 4.00	All the time	Very High (VH)
2.51 - 3.25	Most of the time	High (H)
1.76 - 2.50	Sometime	Low (L)
1.00 - 1.75	Never	Very Low (VL)

In the pretest, the GBL group scored high on *I read instructions carefully before I begin a task* (3.06), *I periodically review to help me understand important relationships* (2.71), *I think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one* (2.68), *I think about what I need to learn before I begin a task* (2.56), and *I am aware of what strategies I use when I study* (2.56). These scores suggest that even before the intervention, students exposed to GBL had already developed certain procedural skills, such as reading instructions thoroughly, reviewing material, and problem-solving.

These findings are in line with Jaaska et al. (2021), who emphasized that games often simulate real-life problem-solving, allowing students to apply procedures actively. However, lower pretest scores were observed in *I ask myself questions about the material before I begin* (2.44), *I find myself using helpful learning strategies automatically* (2.44), *I have a specific purpose for each strategy I use* (2.41), *I try to use strategies that have worked in the past* (2.35), and *I pace myself while learning to have enough time* (2.06). These results indicate that prior to GBL, students had not yet fully developed independent regulation of their learning strategies, aligning with Makalintal and Malaluan (2019), who pointed out that while students may demonstrate strategy use, explicit awareness and control over such strategies often require guided practice and reflection.

In the posttest, students in the GBL group showed significant improvement across all indicators. The highest mean score was recorded for *I read instructions carefully before I begin a task* (3.41), reflecting a *Very High* level of cognitive awareness. Other improved indicators include *I periodically review to help me understand important relationships* (3.00), *I think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one* (3.03), *I think about what I need to learn before I begin a task* (3.09), and *I am aware of what strategies I use when I study* (3.09). Similarly, all remaining indicators showed growth, with students demonstrating increased awareness of their learning strategies. This suggests that game-based learning helped students develop procedural knowledge by promoting self-regulation and strategic learning behaviors. This is supported by Stanton et al. (2021), who emphasized the importance of learner control and metacognitive feedback provided in game-based settings to improve strategic thinking.

For the non-GBL group, students also showed improvement across all indicators in the posttest. The highest scores were recorded for *I read instructions carefully before I begin a task* (2.97), *I periodically review to help me understand important relationships* (2.88), *I think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one* (2.91), *I think*

about what I need to learn before I begin a task (2.97), and I pace myself while learning to have enough time (3.09). These findings suggest that even in a non-game-based learning environment, students were able to develop procedural knowledge through structured classroom instruction and reflective learning practices. Abdelshiheed et al. (2023) support this observation, emphasizing that procedural metacognition can be improved through explicit instruction and guided practice even without the use of games.

The results indicate that while both instructional methods improved students' procedural knowledge, GBL had a stronger impact in fostering self-regulated learning, problem-solving, and the use of effective learning strategies. This aligns with studies by Jaaska et al. (2021), Makalintal and Malaluan (2019), and Stiller and Schworm (2019), which emphasize that game-based learning enhances students' ability to retain knowledge, improve problem-solving skills, and develop perseverance in learning tasks. Furthermore, these findings suggest that a structured and engaging learning environment whether game-based or traditional can positively influence students' procedural knowledge.

Even though the GBL group showed greater improvement, the progress of the non-GBL group shows that guided instruction and practice still play an important role in building metacognitive awareness. According to Lee and Bonk (2025), encouraging students to reflect helps them develop better learning strategies, even in traditional classrooms. This means that no matter the teaching method, helping students reflect on how they learn can improve their procedural knowledge.

The findings show that game-based learning helps strengthen procedural knowledge by making learning more interactive and engaging. The structured and challenge-based design of games may have helped students become more aware of how they solve problems and use learning strategies. This supports the claim of Stanton et al. (2021) that games offer immediate feedback and goal-oriented challenges that cultivate metacognitive awareness. However, the improvements observed in the non-GBL group suggest that procedural knowledge can also be enhanced through traditional instruction when explicit strategy training and reflective learning are prioritized.

Moving forward, educators may explore merging game-based elements with structured classroom practices to maximize the benefits of both methods. Additionally, future research could investigate the long-term impact of game-based and non-game-based learning on students' ability to choose and apply effective methods for learning tasks. These insights underscore the significance of fostering self-regulated learning through instructional methods that promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and strategic learning behaviors.

Conditional knowledge

Table 3 presents students' metacognitive awareness in conditional knowledge, comparing game-based learning (GBL) and non-game-based learning (non-GBL). The pretest mean score for the non-GBL group was 2.34, indicating *Low Cognitive Awareness*, which increased to 2.86 in the posttest, reflecting *High Cognitive Awareness*.

Similarly, the GBL group had a pretest mean score of 2.46, also categorized as *Low Cognitive Awareness*, which improved to 2.93 in the posttest, indicating *High Cognitive Awareness*. These results suggest that both instructional approaches contributed to enhancing students' metacognitive awareness, with the GBL group showing slightly greater improvement. The increase in scores implies that students became more aware of when and why they used specific learning strategies, helping them make better decisions about their learning.

Table 3. Students' metacognitive awareness level under conditional knowledge

Indicators	Pretest				Posttest			
	GBL		Non-GBL		GBL		Non-GBL	
	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI
I can motivate myself to learn when I need to.	2.91	H	2.47	L	3.00	H	2.88	H
I learn best when I know something about the topic.	2.79	H	2.56	H	3.29	VH	3.00	H
I stop and reread when I got confused.	2.59	H	2.24	L	3.06	H	2.68	H
I ask others for help when I don't understand something.	2.44	L	2.41	L	2.85	H	2.97	H
I use different learning strategies depending on the situation.	2.41	L	2.47	L	2.94	H	2.74	H
I use my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses.	2.38	L	2.41	L	2.82	H	2.76	H
I know when each strategy I use will be most effective.	2.35	L	2.44	L	3.02	H	2.62	H
I stop and back over new information that needs to be clarified.	2.29	L	2.32	L	2.94	H	2.85	H
I change strategies when I fail to understand.	2.26	L	2.12	L	2.62	H	3.29	VH

I re-evaluate my assumptions when I got confused.	2.18	L	1.97	L	2.71	H	2.79	H
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WEIGHTED MEAN	2.46	L	2.34	L	2.93	H	2.86	H
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Legend:

<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Rating</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
3.26 - 4.00	All the time	Very High (VH)
2.51 - 3.25	Most of the time	High (H)
1.76 - 2.50	Sometime	Low (L)
1.00 - 1.75	Never	Very Low (VL)

In the pretest, the highest mean scores for the GBL group were recorded in *I can motivate myself to learn when I need to* (2.91), *I learn best when I know something about the topic* (2.79), and *I stop and reread when I get confused* (2.59). These results suggest that prior to the intervention, students already exhibited some awareness of their ability to self-motivate and recognize when prior knowledge helps in learning.

However, lower pretest scores were observed in *I ask others for help when I don't understand something* (2.44), *I use different learning strategies depending on the situation* (2.41), *I use my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses* (2.38), *I know when each strategy I use will be most effective* (2.35), *I stop and revisit new information that needs to be clarified* (2.29), *I change strategies when I fail to understand* (2.26), and *I re-evaluate my assumptions when I get confused* (2.18). These results suggest that students had difficulty adjusting their learning strategies to different situations before Game-based Learning (GBL) and lacked confidence in modifying their approaches when needed. This is in line with the findings of Villareale et al. (2020), who emphasized that students initially lack the metacognitive skills necessary for flexible learning but can develop them through reflective and engaging interventions such as GBL.

Similarly, the pretest scores for the non-GBL group exhibited a comparable trend, with the highest score noted for *I learn best when I know something about the topic* (2.56). Other indicators showed relatively lower mean scores, including *I can motivate myself to learn when I need to* (2.47), *I stop and reread when I get confused* (2.24), *I ask others for help when I don't understand* (2.41), *I use different learning strategies depending on the situation* (2.47), *I use my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses* (2.41), *I know when each strategy I use will be most effective* (2.44), *I stop and revisit new information that needs clarification* (2.32), *I change strategies when I fail to understand* (2.12), and *I re-evaluate my assumptions when I get confused* (1.97). These findings suggest that students in non-GBL settings also faced challenges in adjusting their learning strategies and making necessary changes when encountering difficulties in comprehension. This confirms the observation of Guzman (2019) that without targeted scaffolding or active learning methods, students may struggle with conditional knowledge aspects of metacognition.

In the posttest results, students in the GBL group showed significant improvements across all indicators, with the highest mean score recorded for *I learn best when I know something about the topic* (3.29), indicating a *Very High* level of cognitive awareness. Other indicators also showed notable improvements, including *I can motivate myself to learn when I need to* (3.00), *"I stop and reread when I get confused"* (3.06), *I ask others for help when I don't understand something* (2.85), *I use different learning strategies depending on the situation* (2.94), *I use my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses* (2.82), *I know when each strategy I use will be most effective* (3.02), *I stop and revisit new information that needs to be clarified* (2.94), *"I change strategies when I fail to understand"* (2.62), and *"I re-evaluate my assumptions when I get confused"* (2.71). These results suggest that students in GBL environments became more reflective and strategic learners, particularly in recognizing when prior knowledge supports their learning, when to adjust strategies, and how to seek help when needed. These results further affirm Al-Khayat et al. (2023), who asserted that GBL environments promote self-awareness and decision-making through interactive learning processes that challenge students to assess and adapt their learning strategies in real time.

Similarly, students in the non-GBL group also showed improvement in their conditional knowledge posttest scores, with the highest recorded for *I change strategies when I fail to understand* (3.29), indicating *Very High Cognitive Awareness*. Other indicators also showed growth, including *I can motivate myself to learn when I need to* (2.88), *I learn best when I know something about the topic* (3.00), *I stop and reread when I get confused* (2.68), *I ask others for help when I don't understand something* (2.97), *I use different learning strategies depending on the situation* (2.74), *I use my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses* (2.76), *I know when each strategy I use will be most effective* (2.62), *I stop and revisit new information that needs clarification* (2.85), and *I re-evaluate my assumptions when I get confused* (2.79). These results suggest that traditional classroom settings, when supported by reflective practices and strategy implementation, can also contribute to the development of students' metacognitive awareness.

The findings suggest that both game-based and non-game-based learning approaches effectively enhanced students' conditional knowledge by helping them recognize when and how to use learning strategies. However, GBL appears to provide an advantage in fostering a more self-regulated and strategic approach to learning. GBL's interactive and problem-solving nature likely encouraged students to actively evaluate their learning processes and adjust their strategies in real-time. These findings align with studies by Al-Khayat et al. (2023), which found that GBL enhances motivation, problem-solving, and teamwork, and Villareale et al. (2020), who emphasized the role of reflection during gameplay in improving learning outcomes.

Meanwhile, the results for the non-GBL group indicate that traditional instruction, combined with opportunities for self-reflection, can also strengthen metacognitive skills. This is supported by Guzman (2019), who highlighted that students in conventional learning environments can develop effective strategies through structured guidance and practice. The data suggests that while both methods are beneficial, GBL may offer more immediate and dynamic feedback loops, which are crucial for developing conditional

knowledge and metacognitive adaptability. Moving forward, educators may explore ways to integrate reflective practices into both game-based and traditional learning environments to enhance further students' ability to evaluate, modify, and apply learning strategies effectively.

Table 4 summarizes the students' levels of metacognitive awareness across declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge in both game-based learning (GBL) and non-game-based learning (non-GBL). The pretest results indicate that students in the non-GBL group had an overall mean score of 2.39, suggesting low cognitive awareness. While those exposed to GBL had a higher mean score of 2.52, classified as high cognitive awareness. After the intervention, both groups demonstrated improvements, with the non-GBL group achieving a posttest mean score of 2.88 and the GBL group maintaining a higher mean score of 2.98.

Table 4. Summary of students' metacognitive awareness per construct.

Indicators	Pretest				Posttest			
	GBL		Non-GBL		GBL		Non-GBL	
	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI
Declarative Knowledge	2.57	H	2.51	L	3.03	H	2.92	H
Procedural Knowledge	2.53	H	2.43	L	2.99	H	2.87	H
Conditional Knowledge	2.46	L	2.34	L	2.93	H	2.86	H
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.52	H	2.42	L	2.98	H	2.88	H

Legend:

<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Rating</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
3.26 - 4.00	All the time	Very High (VH)
2.51 - 3.25	Most of the time	High (H)
1.76 - 2.50	Sometime	Low (L)
1.00 - 1.75	Never	Very Low (VL)

These findings indicate that while both instructional methods enhanced students' metacognitive awareness, GBL had a more significant effect. The data in Table 4 further highlight that before the intervention, students in the non-GBL group exhibited low cognitive awareness in all three subskills, while those in the GBL group demonstrated high cognitive awareness in declarative and procedural knowledge but remained at a low level in conditional knowledge. However, after the intervention, both groups achieved high cognitive awareness in all three subskills, with the GBL group consistently outperforming the non-GBL group in posttest scores.

The increase in the non-GBL group's metacognitive awareness, particularly after the intervention, can be attributed to the structured, reflective aspects of traditional learning. In non-game-based learning, students are often provided with specific guidance and instruction that allows them to actively engage with content in a more reflective manner. This approach typically includes activities such as note-taking, discussions, problem-solving, and guided practice, where students are encouraged to pause and reflect on their thought processes. Additionally, traditional learning environments often involve teacher-led discussions and feedback sessions, which provide students with explicit opportunities to reflect on their understanding. This structured feedback encourages students to monitor their thinking, identify areas for improvement, and apply more effective learning strategies moving forward. Research suggests that when students receive consistent feedback and are given opportunities to reflect on their learning in such a structured manner, it can lead to improved metacognitive awareness (Guzman, 2019). The results suggest that game-based learning plays a crucial role in enhancing students' metacognitive skills by providing an engaging and interactive environment where students can actively plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning processes. This supports the findings of Stanton et al. (2021), who emphasize that game-based learning fosters metacognitive growth by encouraging students to reflect on their thought processes. Additionally, Jamon and Lusung-Oyzon (2019) reported that game-based learning leads to more substantial improvements across all stages of metacognition.

However, it is important to recognize that the non-GBL group's improvement in metacognitive awareness also demonstrates the power of traditional teaching methods when combined with opportunities for self-reflection and goal setting. While traditional classroom instruction (non-GBL) also contributed to metacognitive awareness growth, the findings suggest that incorporating game-based elements into teaching strategies may provide additional benefits in fostering self-regulated learning, strategic thinking, and problem-solving skills. Future research may explore how the long-term effects of game-based learning influence students' ability to sustain and further develop their metacognitive awareness beyond the intervention period.

B. Academic Performance of Students in Science 10

Table 5 presents the pretest and posttest scores of students exposed to game-based learning (GBL) and non-game-based learning (non-GBL) in science 10. The data reveals both groups had an MPS below 75, indicating they "Did Not Meet Expectations." The pretest results indicate that students in both groups had an MPS below 75, categorizing them as "Did Not Meet Expectations." The overall mean percentage score (MPS) before the intervention was 34.12% for non-GBL and 37.58% for GBL. These low scores suggest that students had limited prior knowledge of the covered science topics, including the electromagnetic spectrum, light, electricity, and magnetism.

Table 5. Comparison of students' mean scores in the pretest and posttest

Raw Score	Mean % Score	Non-Game Based Learning				Game-Based Learning				DI
		Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
45.00-50.00	90-100	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2.94	O
42.50-44.50	85-89	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	VS
40.00-42.00	80-84	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	S
37.50-39.50	75-79	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	14.70	FS
0-37.00	Below 75	34	100	34	100	34	100	28	82.35	DNME
	Total	34	100	34	100	34	100	34	100	
	MPS	34.12 DNME		40.7 DNME		37.58 DNME		50.94 DNME		

Legend:

<u>Raw Score</u>	<u>Percentage Equivalent</u>	<u>Transmuted Grade</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
45.00-50.00	84.00 to 100	90 to 100	Outstanding (O)
42.50-44.50	76.00 to 83.99	85 to 89	Very Satisfactory (VS)
40.00-42.00	68.00 to 75.99	80 to 84	Satisfactory (S)
37.50-39.50	60.00 to 67.99	75 to 79	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)
0-37.00	0 to 59.99	Below 75	Did Not Meet expectation (DNME)

After the intervention, the posttest results showed improvements in both groups. The non-GBL group attained a mean posttest score of 40.7%, while the GBL group achieved a higher mean score of 50.94%. These gains suggest that both instructional strategies contributed to better content understanding. However, despite the improvements, most students in both groups still did not meet expectations. This may be linked to the difficulty of mastering new concepts in a limited timeframe, indicating that further support and review may be necessary to enhance students' academic performance. One possible reason for this outcome is the series of school activities that affected students' attendance and active participation during the intervention period. As supported by Alajar and Paglinawan (2024), consistent instructional time and student engagement are critical factors in achieving academic success. When students miss lessons due to competing school events, their ability to absorb and apply new concepts may be limited.

This finding highlights the need to address external factors, such as school activities scheduling conflicts, to ensure consistent and continuous learning. This also highlights the importance of ensuring uninterrupted learning sessions and coordinated scheduling to support improved academic outcomes.

Examining the distribution of student performance, the data reveals that one student (2.94%) in the GBL group achieved "Outstanding Performance" (90-100%), while five students (14.70%) reached the "Fairly Satisfactory" level (75-79%). The remaining students in the GBL group (82.35%) continued to fall under "Did Not Meet Expectations."

On the other hand, all students in the non-GBL group remained at the "Did Not Meet Expectations" level, even though their overall mean score slightly increased. This suggests that while some students showed significant improvement, the overall class performance did not meet the expected standards. This may be due to the fact that the intervention period was not long enough for all students to fully benefit from the learning strategies. This indicates that while both instructional approaches contributed to improvement, game-based learning had a greater impact. One possible reason for the limited progress in both groups is the students' inconsistent participation due to overlapping school activities. Many students held responsibilities in the Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG), which required them to miss classes for meetings and events. In addition, frequent student absences may have hindered their full engagement with the lessons. As emphasized by Ancheta et al. (2017), consistent instructional exposure and active participation are critical in enhancing academic performance. Without these, students may struggle to retain concepts and perform well, regardless of the teaching strategy used. The finding highlights the critical role of student engagement and attendance in the success of any instructional strategy, emphasizing that even the most effective methods can be hindered by external factors like inconsistent participation.

The findings align with previous research on the impact of instructional methods on student achievement. Obregon (2021) and Tinambunan & Orongan (2023) found that students with insufficient background knowledge often struggle with comprehension, leading to lower performance. Similarly, Hallberg (2018) emphasized the importance of providing engaging and effective teaching strategies to support student learning and improve their mastery of content. While the GBL group showed higher posttest scores compared to the non-GBL group, the majority of students in both groups still fell under the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category. This suggests that although game-based learning can offer benefits, its impact may be limited when used in isolation or without consistent student participation. The improvement in the GBL group may be partly attributed to increased engagement and motivation, as supported by Tan (2022), who highlights that game-based learning fosters more enjoyable and effective learning experiences. Similarly, Makalintal and Malaluan (2019) found that the use of games enhances student interest and persistence. These results underline the importance of

blending the advantages of game-based learning with other supportive strategies and continuous engagement to maximize its effectiveness.

However, these potential advantages may not have been fully realized in the present study due to external factors such as frequent student absences, school activities, and SSLG responsibilities, which may have disrupted the continuity of learning and limited the intervention's effectiveness. As Papadakis (2018) emphasizes, GBL should be integrated with structured lessons and reflective tasks to maximize its benefits. Furthermore, Rodríguez-Ferrer et al. (2023) argue that blending GBL with differentiated instruction can create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. This further supports the need for a well-rounded instructional approach that combines game-based learning with other methods to ensure all students can benefit from the intervention.

Thus, while GBL has promise, its success depends on careful integration with other instructional supports and consistent student participation. Future studies may explore longer implementation periods and strategies to reduce interruptions, aiming to determine the long-term effects of GBL on academic performance and retention.

Retention Test

Table 6 presents the students' retention mean scores when exposed to non-game-based learning (non-GBL) and game-based learning (GBL). The table shows that both groups have a mean percentile score (MPS) below 75, indicating they "Did Not Meet Expectations".

Table 6. Comparison of students' mean scores in the retention test

Raw Score	Mean Percentage Score	Non-Game Based Learning		Game-Based Learning		Qualitative Interpretation
		N	%	N	%	
45.00-50.00	90-100	0	0	1	2.94	O
42.50-44.50	85-89	0	0	1	2.94	VS
40.00-42.00	80-84	0	0	1	2.94	S
37.50-39.50	75-79	1	2.94	4	11.76	FS
0-37.00	Below 75	33	97.06	27	79.41	DNME
	Total	34	100	34	100	
	MPS(QI)	40.34 (DNME)		54.59 (DNME)		

Legend:

<u>Raw Score</u>	<u>Percentage Equivalent</u>	<u>Transmuted Grade</u>	<u>Descriptive Interpretation</u>
45.00-50.00	84.00 to 100	90 to 100	Outstanding (O)
42.50-44.50	76.00 to 83.99	85 to 89	Very Satisfactory (VS)
40.00-42.00	68.00 to 75.99	80 to 84	Satisfactory (S)
37.50-39.50	60.00 to 67.99	75 to 79	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)
0-37.00	0 to 59.99	Below 75	Did Not Meet expectation (DNME)

The results indicate that both groups had a mean percentile score (MPS) below 75, categorizing them as "Did Not Meet Expectations." The overall mean retention score for the non-GBL group was 40.34%, while the GBL group achieved a higher score of 54.59%. Examining the distribution of retention test scores, the data shows that in the non-GBL group, only one student (2.94%) reached the "Fairly Satisfactory" (75-79%) level, while the majority (97.06%) remained in the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category. In contrast, the GBL group had more students scoring at higher levels, with one student (2.94%) achieving "Outstanding" (90-100%), one student (2.94%) attaining "Very Satisfactory" (85-89%), one student (2.94%) scoring "Satisfactory" (80-84%), and four students (11.76%) reaching the "Fairly Satisfactory" level. Despite these gains, 79.41% of GBL students still did not meet expectations.

These results are consistent with the Self-Determination Theory, which emphasizes that learning is enhanced when students feel motivated and autonomous elements commonly found in GBL environments. The variety of performance levels in the GBL group may reflect individual differences in motivation and engagement fostered by game-based tasks.

The results suggest that while both groups struggled with long-term retention, students exposed to GBL demonstrated better retention scores compared to the non-GBL group. The presence of students achieving higher retention levels (Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, and Fairly Satisfactory) in the GBL group indicates that game-based learning may have helped students recall and apply information more effectively. This supports the Metacognitive Theory, which posits that learning strategies that require students to monitor, evaluate, and regulate their understanding can lead to improved retention. Games often prompt students to use metacognitive skills, such as planning moves and evaluating outcomes, which may have reinforced their grasp of science concepts over time.

In contrast, the non-GBL group showed minimal improvements, with nearly all students remaining in the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category. This suggests that traditional instruction alone may not be sufficient to promote strong knowledge retention over time. However, the results of this study are inconsistent with previous research that found even traditional methods with additional reinforcement or engagement could yield better retention outcomes. For example, studies by Concepcion et al. (2023) and Morales

et al. (2022) suggest that, while traditional methods alone may not be enough, the inclusion of active learning strategies could improve retention.

The findings from this study emphasize the importance of creating a more engaging and interactive learning environment. Despite this, the fact that a majority of students in both groups did not meet expectations highlights the need for additional instructional support. Retention is influenced by multiple factors, including reinforcement activities, review strategies, and long-term engagement with the subject matter. According to Voice & Stirton (2020), retrieval practice and spaced repetition are key strategies for improving long-term retention, as they promote deeper learning and better recall over time.

This suggests that GBL should be blended with structured reinforcement practices, such as formative assessments and periodic reviews, to enhance its effectiveness in retention an approach also supported by the Metacognitive Theory, which underscores the value of reviewing and reflecting on learning progress. Although GBL helped with retention, the results suggest that adding strategies like regular review sessions, reflection activities, and practice tests could improve retention even more. Research supports the idea that spaced repetition, active recall, and regular assessments are key to better long-term learning. Research by Smith & Scarf (2017) supports the idea that spaced repetition significantly enhances retention by increasing the intervals between learning sessions, thereby strengthening memory consolidation.

Moving forward, educators should explore integrating GBL with other instructional techniques, such as concept mapping, peer discussions, and inquiry-based learning, to create a more comprehensive retention strategy. Studies by Collins & Nyenhuis (2020) emphasize the benefits of concept mapping and peer discussions in helping students organize and apply knowledge, which aids in retention. Additionally, future studies may investigate the long-term impact of GBL on retention beyond the immediate posttest period, assessing whether students continue to recall and apply knowledge weeks or months after instruction. A study by Dunlosky et al. (2013) supports this, suggesting that long-term studies are necessary to fully understand the lasting effects of instructional interventions like GBL on retention.

C. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Metacognitive Awareness Between Classes Exposed to Non-GBL and GBL

Table 7 presents the results of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) conducted to compare the posttest metacognitive awareness scores of students exposed to game-based learning (GBL) and non-game-based learning (non-GBL). The mean posttest scores indicate that both groups demonstrated high metacognitive awareness after the intervention. Students in the non-GBL group had a mean score of 2.93 (SD = 0.24), while those in the GBL group had a mean score of 2.88 (SD = 0.18). The ANCOVA results show an F-value of 0.164 with a significance level (p-value) of 0.687, Leads to the acceptance of the null hypotheses indicating that there is no statistically significant

difference between the metacognitive awareness scores of students in the GBL and non-GBL group.

GROUP	N	Mean	SD
Non-Game-based learning	30	2.93	.24
Game-based learning	30	2.88	.18
Total	60	2.93	.22

Table 7: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of students' metacognitive awareness after intervention between classes exposed to non-GBL and GBL.

Source	SS	df	Mean Square	F-value	Sig.
Model	1.184 ^a	2	.59	21.53	.000
Pretest	1.04	1	1.04	37.71	.000
Group	.005	1	.005	.164	.687
Error	1.57	57	.028		
Total	519.191	60			

This suggests that while both instructional strategies led to improvements in students' metacognitive awareness, neither approach proved significantly more effective than the other. This supports the findings of Veenman et al. (2006) who emphasized that metacognitive instruction must be embedded intentionally in the learning process to be effective, regardless of whether the approach is game-based or traditional.

The results also suggest that both GBL and non-GBL approaches are effective in enhancing metacognitive awareness, as reflected in the high posttest scores for both groups. However, the lack of a significant difference implies that the instructional method alone may not be the only factor influencing students' metacognitive development. External elements such as limited class participation due to overlapping school activities, responsibilities in the Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG), and frequent absences likely affected students' ability to fully engage in reflective tasks and structured learning experiences. These factors may have reduced the consistency and depth of their metacognitive development, regardless of the instructional approach used.

These findings align with the study by Yong et al. (2019), which reported that while GBL and non-GBL both improve metacognitive awareness, there is no clear evidence that one method is superior to the other. The results also suggest that metacognitive awareness may develop through structured learning experiences, regardless of whether they are game-based or traditional. Furthermore, research by

Rodríguez-Ferrer et al. (2023) suggests that explicit metacognitive strategy instruction, guided reflection, and one-on-one support could enhance students' metacognitive awareness more effectively than relying solely on instructional method differences. This implies that GBL may be more impactful when combined with structured reflection activities that encourage students to actively monitor and evaluate their thinking processes. A similar study by Tan et al. (2023) found that when GBL is paired with metacognitive training, students show significant improvements in self-regulation and awareness of their learning strategies. This indicates that blending interactive learning with reflective practices can create a more powerful tool for metacognitive development.

On the other hand, non-GBL methods can still foster metacognitive growth, particularly when educators incorporate structured questioning, reflective discussions, and explicit modeling of thinking strategies. A study by Wang (2022) showed that traditional teaching methods, when enhanced with reflective practices such as self-assessment and peer feedback, can still lead to substantial metacognitive growth in students. This underscores that non-GBL strategies can be just as effective in promoting metacognitive awareness when paired with reflective activities that encourage students to analyze their thinking and learning.

Moving forward, educators could explore ways to combine GBL with structured metacognitive activities to maximize its benefits. Research by Barz et al. (2023) supports the integration of GBL with metacognitive tasks, noting that such combinations lead to higher student engagement and better long-term retention of learning outcomes. Future research may also investigate whether longer exposure to GBL results in greater metacognitive gains or if specific instructional modifications can increase its effectiveness in promoting metacognitive awareness. A study by Justo et al. (2022) found that extended exposure to game-based learning led to a noticeable improvement in students' ability to reflect on and regulate their thinking processes, suggesting that the duration of GBL exposure may be a key factor in fostering metacognitive awareness.

D. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Posttest Scores

Table 8 presents the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for the students' academic performance in the posttest, using the pretest as a covariate between groups. The table reveals that students exposed to non-GBL achieved a mean score of 20.38 (SD = 0.26), while those in the GBL group scored 25.47 (SD = 5.51). Furthermore, the F-value was 11.60 ($p > 0.05$) between groups, indicating no significant difference. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, suggesting no significant difference in the academic performance of students exposed to non-GBL compared to those exposed to GBL.

Table 8. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of students' posttest scores

GROUP	N	Mean	SD
Non-Game-based learning	34	20.3824	3.86918
Game-based Learning	34	25.4706	5.51711
Total	68	22.9265	5.37911

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Sig.
Model	510.00 ^a	2	255.00	11.60	.263
Pretest (covariate)	69.87	1	69.87	3.18	.05
Group	355.17	1	355.17	16.16	.20
Error	1428.6	65	21.98		
Total	1938.63	67			

This suggests that although GBL may appear more engaging, academic gains alone may not be sufficient without the reinforcement of reflective learning strategies and consistent instructional support. The results indicate that the GBL group achieved a higher posttest mean score (25.47, SD = 5.52) compared to the non-GBL group (20.38, SD = 3.86). Despite this improvement, the ANCOVA results show an F-value of 11.60 with a significant level ($p > 0.05$), indicating no statistically significant difference between the two groups. This means that while GBL led to higher mean scores, the difference was not significant enough to reject the null hypothesis.

The findings show that students who used GBL performed better than those in the non-GBL group, as seen in their higher posttest scores. This improvement could be due to the interactive and engaging nature of game-based learning, which likely helped students actively participate and apply what they learned. Research by Justo et al. (2022) supports this, showing that GBL increases student engagement and promotes deeper learning.

However, despite the improvement, the lack of statistical significance suggests other factors might have impacted student performance. These factors include prior knowledge, learning styles, and engagement levels, as well as external influences like the classroom environment, teacher effectiveness, and school-related activities. Students involved in extracurricular activities or leadership roles, such as SSLG officers, might struggle to balance academics and responsibilities, affecting their performance. Vargas et al. (2020) found that heavy extracurricular involvement can limit academic focus. Also, frequent absences linked to school events or personal issues may have hurt retention and performance, as noted by Keppens (2023), who found a link between absenteeism and lower academic achievement.

These findings align with Telner et al. (2010), who found improvements in test scores with GBL, but no significant difference compared to traditional teaching. Similarly, Despabiladeras et al. (2024) noted GBL improved retention and engagement but didn't show a significant advantage over conventional methods. However, her study suggested that GBL had a positive impact on critical thinking and deeper understanding, which may not show immediately in test scores but can help in the long term (Gee, 2013; Mao et al., 2021).

While GBL showed positive effects on student performance, the lack of statistical significance suggests that it might work better when combined with other instructional strategies. The data suggests GBL alone might not lead to substantial learning gains but could support understanding and engagement.

Conclusions

The students' metacognitive awareness in both the game-based learning (GBL) and non-game-based learning (non-GBL) groups was classified as "high cognitive awareness" after the intervention. While both groups showed improvement, the GBL group achieved slightly higher mean posttest scores.

Regarding academic performance, students in the GBL group obtained higher posttest and retention test scores than those in the non-GBL group. Suggesting that additional instructional support may be necessary to achieve better learning outcomes.

However, statistical analysis revealed no significant difference between the two groups, indicating that although GBL may enhance metacognitive awareness, it did not lead to significantly superior outcomes compared to non-GBL. Furthermore, statistical analysis showed no significant difference in academic performance between the two groups, lead to accept the null hypothesis. This indicates that while GBL showed potential in engaging students and supporting learning, it was not statistically more effective than traditional methods.

Overall, the study concludes that game-based learning may contribute to improvements in both metacognitive awareness and academic performance. However, as a standalone approach, it was not sufficient to produce statistically significant differences.

Recommendations

Since students under the GBL group demonstrated higher posttest and retention scores, Teachers and curriculum planners may consider incorporating game-based learning (GBL) strategies as an alternative or supplementary method to foster students' metacognitive awareness, as the study indicated that both GBL and non-GBL groups achieved high cognitive awareness, with GBL showing slightly higher gains.

Educators may explore sustained use of GBL to potentially reinforce academic content and support long-term learning retention. School administrators and teachers may provide additional instructional scaffolding or remediation to help students meet the required academic standards, regardless of the learning approach used.

Teachers may still consider it as a tool to enhance student engagement and participation, which are important factors in the learning process.

Future researchers may investigate the long-term effects of game-based learning across different subjects, year levels, or in combination with other instructional strategies, to further explore its potential benefits and limitations in diverse educational settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study strictly followed ethical guidelines to safeguard the rights and welfare of all participants. Prior to data collection, approval letters as well as informed consent and assent forms were obtained. Participants and their parents were clearly informed about the study's objectives and were made aware that their involvement was voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any point. No conflicts of interest were present, and all data gathered were used exclusively for research purposes.

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REFERENCES

- Abdelshiheed, M., Zhou, G., Maniktala, M., Barnes, T., & Chi, M. (2023, March 17). Metacognition and Motivation: The role of Time-Awareness in Preparation for Future learning. arXiv.org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.13541>
- Alajar, F. V., & Paglinawan, J. L. (2024). Beyond the bell: The role of instructional time and learner persistence in shaping effective public-school curricula. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(11), 3123–3132. <https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2024.8110243>
- Al-Khayat, M. R., Gargash, Maha U., & Atiq, A. F. (2023). The Effectiveness of Game-based Learning in Enhancing Students' Motivation and Cognitive Skills. *Journal of Education and Teaching Methods*, 2(3), 50–62. <https://gprjournals.org/journals/index.php/JETM/article/view/199>
- Ancheta, R. F., Daniel, D., & Ahmad, R. (2021). Effect of class attendance on academic performance. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 8(9). <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v8i9.3887>
- Añar, L. E., Barroso, C. J. V., & Manlagaylay, M. P. (2023). The performance of basic education learners in the National Achievement Test. *Journal for ReAttach Therapy and*

- Developmental Diversities, 6(9s), 1520–1535.
<https://jrtd.com/index.php/journal/article/view/1931>
- Barz, N., Benick, M., Dörrenbächer-Ulrich, L., & Perels, F. (2023). The effect of digital game-based learning interventions on cognitive, metacognitive, and affective-motivational learning outcomes in school: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 94(2), 193–227. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543231167795>
- Casildo, N. (2022). Modelling the effect of academic performance on the National Achievement Test (NAT). *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Computer Supported Education*. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0011106300003182>
- Collins, B., & Nyenhuis, R. (2020). The effectiveness of concept maps for students' learning and retention. *Journal of Political Science Education*, 17(Suppl. 1), 897–909.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15512169.2020.1775090>
- Concepcion, G. L., Gole, L. J. T., & Coma, J. F. M. (2023). Game-based instruction: Enhancing the learner's retention in world history subject. *Cognizance Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(11), 366–378. <https://doi.org/10.47760/cognizance.2023.v03i11.030>
- Cruz, Z. (2023). Game-based activities as teaching strategy in chemistry for Grade 9 students. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 11(6), 1–1.
<https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=21582>
- Despabiladeras, G., Lasquite, E., Atayde, E. J., Olvis, K., & Serafico-Reyes, N. M. (2024). Exploring game-based learning (GBL) through learning management systems in teaching Batas Militar (Martial Law) to elementary students' achievement. *TALA: An Online Journal of History*, 7(2), 100–133.
<https://talakasaysayan.org/index.php/talakasaysayan/article/view/208>
- Dunlosky, J., Rawson, K. A., Marsh, E. J., Nathan, M. J., & Willingham, D. T. (2013). Improving students' learning with effective learning techniques: Promising directions from cognitive and educational psychology. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 14(1), 4–58.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1529100612453266>
- Gee, J. P. (2013). Games for Learning. *Educational Horizons*, 91(4), 16–20.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0013175x1309100406>
- Guzman, S.-A. C. (2019). Metacognitive Awareness and Academic Performance in English of Grade 7 Students. *SPUP Graduate School Research Journal*, 15(2). Retrieved from <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/spupgsrj/article/view/423>
- Jamon, K. G. G., & Lusung-Oyzon, M. V. P. (2019). Utilizing Teaching Games for Understanding in Physical Education: Effects on primary students' metacognition. *Alipato: A Journal of Basic Education*, 10, 1–20.
- Jääskä, E., & Aaltonen, K. (2022). Teachers' experiences of using game-based learning methods in project management higher education. *Project Leadership and Society*, 3, 100041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plas.2022.100041>
- Justo, R. C., Ramos, R. F., Llandelar, S. M. R., Sanares, R. N., & Rodelas, N. C. (2022). Game-based learning for student engagement: A paradigm shift in blended learning education. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2502, 050002. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0109625>
- Keppens, G. (2023). School absenteeism and academic achievement: Does the timing of the absence matter? *Learning and Instruction*, 86, 101769.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2023.101769>
- Lee, H., & Bonk, C. J. (2024). Fostering self-directed learning competencies among preservice teachers through reflective practice and technology-mediated collaborative learning. *Technology Pedagogy and Education*, 1–17.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1475939x.2024.2362853>
- Makalintal, J. D., & Malaluan, N. E. (2019). Game-based learning activities in teaching Grade 7 science. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3241249>

- Maniego, E. S. (2021). Academic disposition and metacognitive knowledge on learners' achievement in Alternative Learning System [Unpublished dissertation]. PHINMA Cagayan de Oro College.
- Mao, W., Cui, Y., Chiu, M. M., & Lei, H. (2021a). Effects of game-based learning on students' critical thinking: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 59(8), 1682–1708. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07356331211007098>
- Morales, R. A., Alava, W. G., & Bello, A. Q. (2022). Effects of Multiple Game-based Strategies in Grade 10 Science Learning. *CMU Journal of Science*, 26(2), 120-130. <https://doi.org/10.52751/ZZOY6467>
- OECD. (2023). PISA 2022 results (Volume I): The state of learning and equity in education. PISA, OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/53f23881-en>
- OECD. (2023). PISA 2022 results (Volume II). Programme for International Student Assessment. <https://doi.org/10.1787/a97db61c-en>
- Obregon, J. (2021). Enhancing Students' Engagement and Academic Performance through Simulation based Cybergogy Learning Environment. (Unpublished Master's Thesis). Central Mindanao University Graduate School.
- Papadakis, S. (2018). The use of computer games in classroom environment. *International Journal of Teaching and Case Studies*, 9(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijtc.2018.090191>
- Rodríguez-Ferrer, J. M., Manzano-León, A., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., & Cangas, A. (2023). Effectiveness of gamification and game-based learning in Spanish adolescents with dyslexia: Longitudinal quasi-experimental research. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 141, 104603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2023.104603>
- Saaidin, N. (2020). The influence between metacognition practice, students' learning commitment and academic achievement of matriculation students in physics. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v10-i3/7351>
- Simbajon, J. S., & Adlaon, M. S. (2024). Learning Gaps and Proficiency Levels in Science Specialized Subjects of Senior High School Students in Surigao City, Philippines. *International Journal of Research*, 11(5), 138–158. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195269>
- Smith, C. D., & Scarf, D. (2017). Spacing repetitions over long timescales: A review and a reconsolidation explanation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 962. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00962>
- Stanton, J. D., Sebesta, A. J., & Dunlosky, J. (2021). Fostering metacognition to support student learning and performance. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 20(2). <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.20-12-0289>
- Stiller, K. D., & Schworm, S. (2019). Game-based learning of the structure and functioning of body cells in a foreign language: Effects on motivation, cognitive load, and performance. *Frontiers in Education*, 4, Article 18. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2019.00018>
- Tan, W., Supian, N., & Cheah, K. S. (2022, January 5). Game-based learning in improving English vocabulary and detecting metacognitive awareness among English for specific purposes undergraduates. Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.220101.021>
- Tan, W., Supian, N., & Cheah, K. S. (2023). Using game-based learning in developing metacognition among ESP students: A case study. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 19(3), 506–518. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v19i3.23495>
- Taran, E. L., & Nalla, H. R. R. (2019). Metacognitive awareness and attitudes toward problem-solving in science of senior high school students. *Journal of Advances in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(1), 33–43.
- Telner, D., Bujas-Bobanovic, M., Chan, D., et al. (2010). Game-based versus traditional case-based learning: Comparing effectiveness in stroke continuing medical education. *Canadian Family Physician*, 56, 345–351.

- Tinambunan, S. R. N., & Orongan, M. J. Q. (2023). Game-based learning on students' motivation and academic achievement in science 9. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development MPS*, 10, 20–19. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368396989>
- Vargas, M., Calesterio, R., Gutierrez, R., Morales, D., Zapanta, J. A., & Amar, J. (2020). Effects of extracurricular on academic performance of senior high school students of Bestlink College of the Philippines: Toward a guide. Ascendens Asia Singapore – Bestlink College of the Philippines *Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1). Retrieved from <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/aasgbcpjmra/article/view/2464>
- Vilanueva, L. M. M. (2024). Improving science performance through games: An analysis of game-based learning in Earth and Life Science. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 22(2), 1633–1636. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.2.1614>
- Veenman, M. V. J., Van Hout-Wolters, B. H. A. M., & Afflerbach, P. (2006). Metacognition and learning: Conceptual and methodological considerations. *Metacognition and Learning*, 1(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-006-6893-0>
- Villareale, J., Biemer, C. F., El-Nasr, M. S., & Zhu, J. (2020). Reflection in Game-Based Learning: A Survey of Programming Games. *Foundations of Digital Games 2020*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3402942.3403011>
- Voice, A., & Stirton, A. (2020). Spaced repetition: Towards more effective learning in STEM. *New Directions in the Teaching of Physical Sciences*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.29311/ndtps.v0i15.3376>
- Wang, Y. (2022). A comparative study on the effectiveness of traditional and modern teaching methods. In *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research/Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research* (pp. 270–277). https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-494069-89-3_32
- Yong, S. T., Gates, P., & Chan, A. T. (2018). Similarities and differences in learning of metacognitive skills. *International Journal of Game-Based Learning*, 9(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijgbl.2019010101>
- Zepeda, C. D., Richey, J. E., Ronevich, P., & Nokes-Malach, T. J. (2015). Direct instruction of metacognition benefits adolescent science learning, transfer, and motivation: An in vivo study. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 107(4), 954–970. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000022>